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Why Digital Pedagogy for School Education? An Overview

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Abstract:

In India, the trend of online and ICT-based tools and technologies in the education system has increased significantly immediately following the Covid-19 pandemic. Along with this, the concept of Digital

Pedagogy as an innovation has come in front of all of us. However, it cannot be denied that due to the sudden shift of the entire education system to online mode during the pandemic, many problems have come to the fore at different levels of education. Certainly, these problems can be reduced by the successful use of digital pedagogy. The NEP 2020 has also officially recognized the role of digital pedagogy in the Indian education system (primary to post graduate). Special provisions have also been made for its promotion and implementation in the NEP 2020 and the Union Budget 2022-23. At present, the way the trend of online and ICT-based tools and techniques is increasing rapidly in the field of education, digital pedagogy is about choosing the right online and ICT-based tools and techniques carefully and using other beneficial educational techniques from the educational point of view. Digital Pedagogy emphasizes the intelligent use of online and ICT-based tools and techniques in the educational process and monitors how these tools are affecting learning. This is such an innovation that when used in the educational process, it gives new learning experiences to the teacher, student, and the entire class. Where new possibilities arise for learning in which learning is not limited to students or teachers but is collaborative, in this article, the researcher has tried to explain in simple words the prevalent digital pedagogy educational innovation since the Covid-19 pandemic and to clarify its need and relevance at present.

Keywords: Digital pedagogy, Meaningful Learning, School Education

Introduction:

According to an estimate, there are about 15 lakh schools in India. About 18 lakh teachers are doing teaching work in these schools. India has more than 900 universities, more than 50000 colleges, and around 10 million teachers working at all levels of education across the country. In such a situation, because of the increasing trend of online and ICT-based tools in the field of education and

understanding its need in the future, the NEP 2020 has included in its document to promote digital education in India and train a large number of teachers for it. Special provisions have been kept. The NEP 2020 has said in its report that every teacher should develop as a digital teacher so that according to the requirements of the 21st century, communication, cooperation, and critical thinking can be used in the educational process and the process of problem-solving can be doubled. In India's Union Budget 2022-23, the financial allocation has been ensured for the inclusion of digital pedagogy in the courses of different levels of education and its effective implementation. In the budget, special attention has been given to the fact that keeping in mind the needs of the present time, facilities like Virtual Labs, 3-D Modeling, Google Cloud, Flip Classroom, crossover teaching, etc. will be provided to the students and digital pedagogy should be used for this. For example, there are many experiences for students that may be risky or not environmentally friendly for them to experience in the field. For example, going to the mouth of an active volcano to see and experience the whole process of an active volcano's eruption can be risky. Similarly, to understand the nature and structure of the internal organs of a frog in a biology class, it has to be dissected under experiment, which is not compatible with the environmental values. The use of such virtual labs as a component of digital pedagogy reduces the potential risk to students in learning and understanding new knowledge and enables them to have a personalized experience within the classroom. Similar other online and ICT-based tools can be chosen by the teachers wisely according to the need of the students.

Linguistically, there is a wide diversity in India, according to a report, more than 1700 languages are spoken in India and there are 5 different language families. The NEP 2020 has proposed that the primary education of children should be in their mother tongue so that the speed of learning can be increased. Digital Pedagogy In this context, to teach students of different languages in their language, to choose the right tool from a variety of online and ICT-based tools (such as OneNote, Google Jamboard, Miro, Heilama, DeepL, etc.) and assist teachers in developing new tools to create new opportunities to facilitate and accelerate learning that may be able to provide new experiences to students as well as teachers.

The real objective of promoting digital pedagogy is that our teachers and students can meet global standards keeping in mind global needs. Teaching through digital pedagogy in a blended mode in the educational process by judiciously choosing appropriate online and ICT-based tools and striking the right balance between other beneficial educational activities such as critical thinking, collaborative learning, individual learning, etc. to enrich the learning process. Recently U.G.C. released a document to promote Blended Learning in which UGC has proposed to include 60% physical and 40% digital pedagogy in the educational

process. This proportion of pedagogy is proposed to be extended from nursery to tertiary and from pre-primary to higher education.

Historical overview of digital pedagogy:

Historically, the beginning of digital pedagogy can be seen in the development of distance education. In 1858, the University of London conducted its first distance degree course. Since then, till the early 1970s, similar courses started running in other universities in Europe and America. Such courses paved the way for online education with the rise in popularity of the Internet in this era. In the 1980s and 1990s, various workshops on humanities and computer education were organized by mutual cooperation of computers and humanities. The national endowment for the humanities was established in 1965. Under which the office of digital humanity was established in 2008. Since then, the conference on Digital Pedagogy is organized annually in different countries.

The theoretical background of digital Pedagogy:

We find the roots of digital pedagogy in the **social approach of constructivism**. In the process of teaching-learning, teachers try to provide opportunities to the students in which they can make their own understanding of the concepts by choosing online and ICT-based tools according to their convenience and follow up the discussion and collaboration with peers as well as teachers.

Criteria for exclusion and inclusion of articles

In the presented article, keeping in mind the following points, articles have been selected for review.

- a. Articles, books and documents were selected in which digital pedagogy was at the center.
- b. Since digital pedagogy is an emerging field, priority was given to articles related to its theoretical background and conceptual background.
- c. Only articles related mainly to digital pedagogy and school education were included in the review.
- d. Those articles from the year 2020 to the year 2022 were included in the study which fulfill the above-mentioned points.
- e. Only those articles were included for the study which were in English language.
- f. The articles were selected from journals, books and documents of international and national repute.

Selection Process

The articles listed in Table 1 below have been shortlisted for review for this research.

Table 1: List of shortlisted articles for review:

No.	Title of the Article	Author	Source	Year	Methodology/Tools	Context/Participants
1.	The Emerging Concept of the Digital Pedagogy	Cabanero, E. J et al.,	International Journal of Academic Pedagogical Research (IJAPR) ISSN: 2643-9123 Vol. 6 Issue 4, April - 2022, Pages:63-67	2022	Critically evaluates the research on digital pedagogy that is available in various databases starting in May 2020.	Review based article, secondary data was used for analysis
2.	The educational response to Covid-19 across two countries: a critical examination of initial digital pedagogy adoption	Greenho, C, et al.,	Journal of Technology, Pedagogy, and Education, Taylor&Francis Online	2021	An interpretive paradigm approach to qualitative case study.	Articles, columns, and editorials about K-12 education that appeared in print or online news media were also included.
3.	Digital Pedagogy for Sustainable Learning	C Nanjundaswamy Baskaran Subburaman and M H Leela	Shanlax International Journal of Education, Vol. 9, Issue:3, pp. 179-185	2021	Analysis of secondary data	Conceptual Study the secondary data was sourced from websites, eBooks, and publications.
4.	Conceptualizing dimensions and a model for digital pedagogy	Vaataja, O. J & Ruokamo, Heli	Journal of Pacific Rim Psychology, Volume 15: 1-12, Sage Publication	2021	Critically examine the researches available in the different databases related to digital pedagogy from May 2020 onwards	Review based article based on secondary data

5.	Digital Pedagogy: Problems and Solutions	Liliia V. Volkava, Larisa R. Lizunova And Iuliia A. Komarova	Revista on line de Politica e Gestao Educacional, Vol. 25, Esp. 5, 2021	2021	Analysis of scientific literature related to digital pedagogy	Secondary data related to digital pedagogy were used
6.	Narrativizing Digital Pedagogy	Aaron R. Gierhart and Robyn Seglem	International Journal of Qualitative Studies in Education Published by Taylor & Francis(Routledge)	2021	Narrative research methods	Conceptual article based on narrative research method
7.	Digital Pedagogy with ICT and Learning Technologies	Das, A & Bag, R	Book, CBS Publishers, 978-93-89688-47-4	2020	Theoretical framework established with ICT and Learning Technologies	Primary and Secondary source of data used as well as phenomenological approach
8.	Digital Pedagogy Analysis, requirements and experience of implementation	Toktarova, V. I & Semanova, D. A	Journal of Physics: Conference Series, IOP Publishing	2020	Content analysis and discursive analysis	Based on secondary data source across the online mode.

For this article, we went through these articles which are listed in Table 1. We can say there are a variety of articles that covers different dimensions related to digital pedagogy. Researcher analysis each and every article and based on their understanding try to explain the concept of digital pedagogy through their lens. A few important zest articles are cited below.

Jerwin E. Cabanero et. al, (2022) conducted a study on the emerging concept of digital pedagogy in their research work researchers explained the concept of digital pedagogy for this they used secondary data sources and online resources. Christine et. al. (2021) explicit in their research work critically examines the initial use of digital pedagogy during the covid-19 pandemic. In this research work qualitative case study was done of print and media articles that were shortlisted for the study. C. N. B. S. and M. H. Leela (2021) conducted a study based on secondary data in their research work they were focused on conceptual understanding of digital pedagogy. Das, A. and Bag, R, (2020) published a book on digital pedagogy because we know that digital pedagogy is an emerging field of research. So for understanding the theoretical and conceptual background of digital pedagogy this book really helpful for k-12 teachers as well students.

What is digital pedagogy?

The use of online and digital technologies, such as augmented reality, virtual reality, networked computers, mobile technologies, artificial intelligence, etc., has become more prevalent in the field of education at the moment. These include Socrative, Scratch, Storybird, Animoto, Cahoot, Prezi, Selfcad, Quizlet, Google Classroom, Adobespark Video, Khan Academy, Seesaw, Clasdojo, Flexibility, etc. Additionally, numerous online and ICT-based tools for education have been developed.

How can online and ICT-based tools and techniques be used in the educational process even today? Scholars do not have a single opinion on this, so it remains an important topic of discussion even today. On the other hand, there is a sizable number of professionals and academics who think that using digital tools and technology in education might help students gain access to new knowledge structures and ways of knowing (Kelly, 2010). On the other hand, there is a lot of criticism about how educational institutions adopt online and ICT-based tools and techniques for teaching-learning. Researches shows that online and ICT-based tools and technologies have the transformative power to enhance learning, but we must not forget that online and ICT-based tools and technologies are not yet delivering the results we were hoping for. In the context of India, we all have experienced this in the last almost three years when the entire education system was converted into an online medium during the Covid-19 period. Our experiences show that the sudden shift of the entire education system to online mode has brought many challenges in front of students, teachers, parents, school heads, and policymakers. Therefore, before utilising online and ICT-based tools and strategies in the teaching-learning process, one should give the matter some serious thought. To ensure that we properly choose online and ICT-based tools and strategies for the educational process, the notion of digital pedagogy has caught the attention of students and teachers in this situation. In order to attain the learning results we want.

Digital pedagogy is still a young academic discipline (Baldick, 2016). There is no universally accepted definition of digital pedagogy. Different experts have given different definitions of it. It is also known by many other names such as e-learning pedagogy, online pedagogy, e-pedagogy, etc. Digital pedagogy is not completely different from online and I.C.T. Based education. It offers a guide for implementing online and ICT-based resources in the classroom to ensure that both students and teachers face the fewest obstacles possible. If we talk about some inclusive definitions of digital pedagogy, then they are as follows-

According to **Tan & Subramaniam, (2013)** the purpose of digital pedagogy is to achieve effective learning through the appropriate and careful use of online and ICT-based tools and techniques.

According to **Vataja & Rukamo, (2021)** the use of online and ICT-based tools and approaches while keeping in mind the pedagogical requirements is known as digital pedagogy.

Simply put, digital pedagogy is the study of how to effectively use online, digital, and ICT-based resources, which are being used in large numbers in the field of education at present. It is necessary for teachers to be trained in digital pedagogy because by using digital pedagogy, they understand which online and ICT-based tools they have to choose to achieve a particular educational objective? And In what quantity? And how will it impact education? Digital pedagogy can be applied in face-to-face, hybrid, and online settings.

Digital pedagogy encompasses access to or selection of online and ICT-based tools from a critical pedagogical perspective as well as the use of online technologies and tools in the educational process. It involves using online and ICT-based technologies responsibly and choosing when to use and when not to use them. How can the intended learning outcomes for a class be easily attained by the appropriate usage of various online and ICT-based tools? Through the thoughtful selection of online and ICT-based tools in a blended learning environment with online, hybrid, or face-to-face modes of instruction, digital pedagogy seeks to bring learning closer to an experience-based environment. Aiming to create a learning environment where there is greater collaboration, a more enjoyable learning experience, the potential for greater asset creation, as well as a greater personalised and more purposeful learning experience can be provided to each student, digital pedagogy uses online and ICT-based tools in the classroom with the appropriate choice and proportion of other teaching methods. Where pupils may hear and observe learning being done. The idea of digital pedagogy is not simply restricted to enhancing student learning experiences; it is also capable of offering teachers new and exciting learning opportunities. Simply put, we may say that when digital pedagogy is used in the classroom, both the teacher and the student encounter new types of learning.

An article on digital pedagogy published by Oxford University Press (2022) highlights that when students learn through devices and used online and ICT-based tools, their learning speed, and methods are different. In such a situation, the role of digital pedagogy emerges, which works to provide a personalized experience to the students through mixed media by choosing the right online and ICT-based tools keeping in mind the educational approach and individual differences, and in harmony with other beneficial teaching methods.

Diagram: 1 Concept map of Digital Pedagogy

Diagram: 1 Concept map of Digital Pedagogy

(Source: The researcher has prepared this diagram himself.)

Key Features of Digital Pedagogy

The characteristics of digital pedagogy in the educational process are mentioned below point-wise-

- In digital pedagogy, online and ICT-based tools for the educational process are selected preserving the pace of learning and the students' demands.
- It uses a combination of other collaborative learning methods along with the choice of the right online and ICT-based tools to personalize student experiences.

- In the process of teaching-learning, special care is taken for the association and cooperation of the students with each other and with the teacher so that the learning becomes collaborative.
- Through digital pedagogy, teachers not only collect new learning experiences for themselves but also work to provide new experiences for the whole class.
- In this type of pedagogy, students use questions for learning and engage in a dialogue process that is dynamic and constantly changing.
- Digital pedagogy promotes engagement and collaboration in the educational process by choosing the right digital technologies and tools such as web 2.0, virtual laboratories, 3-D modeling, etc. to provide personalized experiences to the students.

Key Principles of Digital Pedagogy

As we have already understood what is Digital Pedagogy? And how it is different from online and I.C.T. based education? The objective of digital pedagogy is to strengthen the educational process by further enriching meaningful learning with the help of internet tools. Digital Pedagogy mainly works on three principles which are as follows-

1. Offering Choices
2. Identifying the level of Difficulties for the students
3. Opportunity for Collaboration

Diagram: 2 Principles of Digital Pedagogy

(Source: The researcher has prepared this diagram himself.)

1. Offering Choice

The learning styles of students differ in the educational process. Researches in neuroscience suggest that just as the fingerprints of each person are different, in the same way, the learning style of each student is also different. Students use different learning styles to learn different subjects. Keeping this variability in the learning of students, it is not justified to teach them with one method or one internet tool. Digital Pedagogy provides a simple opportunity for students through which students can choose their online and ICT-based tools to learn according to their ability and their choice, due to which the learning process of the student is more enjoyable and interesting. For example, teachers can provide subject matter to students in their mother tongue by the use of a variety of tools, show an event happening through Virtual Labs, and develop such online tools for evaluation which different students can choose according to their convenience, etc.

2. Identifying the level of Difficulties for the students

As we know that the learning style of each student is different, in the same way, during the process of teaching-learning, while solving a task or a problem, students have to face different levels of problem. For example, a student may find a problem difficult in the beginning while another student may find the same problem easy in the beginning, in the same way, a student may find some steps at the beginning of a problem easy while the middle Or the end stages may seem a bit difficult, so it is not a good idea to provide the same scaffolding for all the students in any class. Therefore, digital pedagogy emphasizes that the individual learning styles of students and their learning problems should be understood by the teachers in the educational process so that meaningful learning can take place in the educational process.

3. Opportunity to Collaboration

Research suggests that when students learn in groups, they are most likely to learn meaningfully, so digital pedagogy emphasizes that the educational process should not be one-sided, that is, one-way an environment should be created in which both students and teachers get new experiences and move forward with cooperation in the process of learning.

How does meaningful learning happen?

We know that the whole thrust of digital pedagogy is on doubling the speed of learning, facilitating learning, and providing new learning experiences by engaging students and teachers collectively in the learning process. So before we discuss the subject of digital pedagogy it is necessary to know how does meaningful learning take place?

According to the famous psychologist David Ausubel's Meaningful Verbal Learning Model 1960, meaningful learning occurs only when the students are

involved in the process of learning new concepts in the educational process and they make a strong connection between the new information and the old information. Students understand this relationship according to their ability and convenience or see it being made. To promote meaningful learning, the following processes are included which are as follows-

- Teaching should be inquiry-based, with a sense of reward involved.
- Learning should be experiential and collaboration should be encouraged during the process.
- Teaching should be linked to the social and emotional background of learning.
- Teaching should be multimodal and collaborative.

Diagram: 3 Activities for meaningful learning

(Source: The researcher has prepared this diagram himself.)

Through digital pedagogy, the above-mentioned activities are included in the process of teaching-learning by careful selection of different types of online and ICT-based tools so that simple learning can be taken towards meaningful learning.

Role of Teacher in Digital Pedagogy

Knowing that the function of the instructor in face-to-face instruction is not diminished by incorporating digital pedagogy into teaching and learning is essential to understanding the notion of digital pedagogy. The importance of teachers in the educational process hasn't changed over time. The shift has been

brought about by the employment of digital pedagogy in the educational process. Through the careful selection of online and ICT-based tools and approaches from the standpoint of education, an effort is being made to make learning more thorough and purposeful. So that we can use different online and ICT-based tools as per the requirement of the nature of the subjects and the learning experience can be made comprehensive, accessible, and personalized by using online and ICT-based tools. UNESCO-MGIEP Delhi, and C.I.E.T. (NCERT) has taken steps for the promotion and implementation of digital pedagogy proposed in National Education Policy-2020. NCERT has successfully organized a 5-day training program on Digital Pedagogy in the last week of July 2022. UNESCO-MGIEP, category 1 research institute at Delhi is also currently conducting a certificate course in India called Digital Teacher, in which the main emphasis is on how teachers can effectively use digital technologies.

How can school teachers use digital pedagogy?

We are aware that digital pedagogy goes beyond the simple use of online and ICT-based tools in the educational process (such as 3-D Modelling, Tingling, TED-Ed, ClassDojo, Web 2.0, Virtual Labs, etc.); rather, it is a pedagogy that aims to move learning towards meaningful learning and give students and teachers new experiences. It is obvious that there will be greater use of digital pedagogy at the elementary level in the future given how the NEP 2020 and the Government of India have fought to encourage its usage in the educational process. If we talk from the point of view of school teachers, digital pedagogy can be helpful in many ways to promote meaningful learning in classes at the school level in the future, which are written point-wise below-

1. By carefully choosing a variety of digital equipment

We understand that digital pedagogy helps teachers to choose tools in the educational process keeping in mind the educational objectives. In today's time, new online and ICT-based tools and techniques are being invented in the field of education for example Socrative, Scratch, Prezi, Selfcad, Quizlet, Storybird, Animoto, Cahoot, Google Classroom, Adobe Spark Video, Khan Academy, Seesaw, dojo, flexibility, etc. which tools to use in such a situation? And for how long? This is important. In such a situation, digital pedagogy helps teachers choose the right online and ICT-based tools keeping in mind the educational objectives.

2. Promoting dialogue and discussion in a learning environment

A major quality of digital pedagogy is that the learning process is never one-sided, that is, teachers and students learn from each other by using online and ICT-based tools in the process of teaching-learning, communicating, and discussing them. The misconceptions about the concepts in the minds of the students are revealed and clarified with the help of suitable examples.

3. By providing new experiences to the students

Using digital pedagogy, a variety of online and ICT-based tools can be used in the classroom to explain a concept at a time keeping in mind the need of the students and their pace of learning which provides a new experience to both student and teacher. Especially students can choose digital equipment according to their convenience. For example, if students from different linguistic backgrounds are present in a class, the teacher can provide them with the translation of the content and lectures in their mother tongue which certainly provides new personal experiences to the students and empowers the learning process.

4. By promoting collaboration in the learning process

Collaboration has its special place in the learning process because through this we can get many students to participate in the learning process which positively refines the learning environment. By using digital pedagogy, a sense of cooperation is promoted in the process of teaching-learning, so that learning becomes multimodal rather than self-centric. This new experience is capable of leading the students toward meaningful learning.

Conclusion:

It cannot be denied that in today's time technology has reached a new level. In various sectors, the technology has proved its efficacy in terms of quality. In the field of education also, in the last two decades, the trend of new technologies has increased a lot, in which online and I.C.T.-based technology has carved a niche for itself. In the educational process at the time of the covid-19 pandemic in the whole world including India, suddenly online and I.C.T. based devices has grown tremendously as well as the need for such devices in the future is better understood. Digital Pedagogy provides a better option for how to use online and ICT-based tools keeping in mind the psychological rules in the process of learning. Digital pedagogy is capable of accelerating the pace of learning in the educational process and providing new educational experiences to students while learning. It focuses on the selection of online and ICT-based tools in a classroom taking into account individual differences and differences in student learning speeds. Digital Pedagogy works to empower meaningful learning by providing new experiences to teachers as well as students at the various level of education. The trend of digital pedagogy will increase in the coming times and it will also helpful in providing new learning opportunities to teachers and students.

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